

TABLE 3—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY OF TYPE I AND II

Sl. No.	R	Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 μ g conc/disk		Mycobact. antituberculosis activity ($H_{37} R_v$)	Interpretation zone of inhibition at 100 μ g conc/disk	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	-	-	+	-	-
2.	-2.OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
3.	-5.Br.2.OH.C ₆ H ₃	+	-	+	+	-
4.	-3,5-di-Bromo-2-OH. -C ₆ H ₃	++	+	+	++	+
5.	-2.Cl.C ₆ H ₄	-	-	-	-	-
6.	-C ₄ H ₉ O	-	-	+	-	-
7.	-4.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	++	+	+	+	+
8.	-3.NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	-	-
9.	-CH=CH.C ₆ H ₅	+	+	+	+	+
10.	-4.OH.3.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	++	+	+	++	+
11.	-4.OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
12.	-3.OH.C ₆ H ₄	-	-	+	-	-
13.	-4.CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
14.	-4.N(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-
15.	-4.OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-	+	+	-

Columns 3 to 5 indicate activity of thiosemicarbazones.

Columns 6 and 7 indicate activity of thiadiazolinylns.

+ = zone diameter less than 20 mm ; ++ = zone diameter more than 20 mm ; - = no inhibition.

aqueous potassium ferricyanide solution (5%) added dropwise with shaking ceased further precipitation. The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water to remove potassium ferricyanide and crystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. recorded in Table 2.

Antitubercular activity: *In vitro* antitubercular activity of the hitherto synthesised thiosemicarbazone derivatives was studied against $H_{37} R_v$ strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 μ g/ml and the retardation of the growth rate was recorded upto 6 weeks at 37° (Table 3).

Antibacterial activity: The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by N-agar pour plate method in dimethylformamide and they were found to be active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* in various concentration (Table 3).

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) and Stepwise Formation Constants of Its Complexes with N-(4-Methoxy-phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide and N-(4-Methyl-phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide

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THE spectrophotometric determination of palladium are numerous but still there are very few selective reagents where the other platinum group metals do not interfere. It was suggested¹⁻³ that the substituted dithio-oxamides are very sensitive reagents for trace determination of palladium. It was found^{4,5} that reagents containing the nitroso-phenylamine group (e.g. *p*-nitrosodiphenyl aniline) are one of the most sensitive reagents for palladium. The other important sensitive and selective reagents reported are 2-aldehyde 2-quinolylylhydrazones⁶, 1-(2-carboxy-4-sulfonato phenyl) 3-hydroxy-3-phenyl triazine⁷, promethazine hydrochloride⁸, N,N' bis-(3-dimethyl-aminopropyl) dithio-oxamide⁹, phenyl α -pyridyl ketoxime¹⁰, and 1-(2-pyridyl azo)-2-naphthol¹¹. The review¹² reported several organic reagents for photometric determination of palladium and they are mainly organic acids, dyes, heterocyclic bases, triazines, oximes and sulphur bearing ligands.

The present investigation attempts to find some chromogenic reagents for palladium with sulphur and nitrogen as donor atoms. Effect on sensitivity with change of functional groups were also investigated. The method was extended to the

determination of palladium in synthetic mixture. The stepwise formation constants k_1 and k_2 of the complexes PdL_1^+ and PdL_2 , respectively have been evaluated following the graphical extrapolation methods of Leden¹⁸ and Yatsimirskii¹⁴⁻¹⁶. The overall formation constants of the palladium complexes has also been evaluated by Harvey-Manning method.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer and Spektromom 204 with 1 cm quartz cells were used for recording absorption.

Synthesis of reagents : The reagent I was prepared¹⁷ by refluxing *p*-anisidine (2 mol), α -picoline (1 mol) and sulphur powder (1.5 mol). The thio-compound was isolated by repeated extraction of the oily mass with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The petroleum ether was evaporated and the solid yellow mass was recrystallized twice from absolute ethanol; yield of the product 20% (based on α -picoline). m.p. 95° (Found : C, 63.68 ; H, 4.56 ; N, 11.60 ; S, 13.20. Calcd. : C, 63.93 ; H, 4.92 ; N, 11.48 ; S, 13.11%).

The reagent II was similarly prepared by refluxing *p*-toluidine (2-mol), α -picoline (1 mol) and sulphur powder (1.5 mol) to yield the product, m.p. 97° (Found : C, 68.18 ; H, 4.71 ; N, 11.96 ; S, 14.20. Calcd. : C, 68.42 ; H, 5.26 ; N, 12.28 ; S, 14.04%).

A standard solution of Pd^{2+} was prepared by dissolving 1g ampule of $PdCl_2$ (Johnson Matthey) in 1M hydrochloric acid and standardised by estimating as dimethyl glyoximate¹⁸. A freshly prepared reagent I (0.1%) and reagent II (0.2%) in chloroform medium were used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Application of the methods : The synthetic mixture (50 ml) containing Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Ir^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} and Os^{8+} was treated with sulphuric acid (6 N, 5 ml), followed by a few drops of potassium permanganate solution to oxidise Os^{6+} to Os^{8+} . Ferrous ammonium sulphate (25 mg) was added to discharge excess of permanganate. The solution was cooled to 5° and hydrogen peroxide (30 vol., 15 ml) was added. The Os^{8+} was extracted quantitatively^{2,4} using 10 ml portions of chloroform. Then Pd^{2+} was extracted with chloroform following the recommended procedure with reagent I or II.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectra of 3.75×10^{-5} M Pd^{2+} with reagent I and 7.50×10^{-5} M Pd^{2+} with reagent II were recorded following the optimum conditions. It was found that both the complexes have λ_{max} at 440 nm.

Effect of acidity and reagent concentrations : The complexes showed constant colour intensity from

1.6 to 3.2 M HCl for reagent I and 2.4 to 4.0 M for reagent II, respectively. The optimum reagent concentration where the absorbances remains constant is from 2.0 to 3.5 ml of 0.1% reagent I, and 2.5 to 6.0 ml of 0.2% reagent II in chloroform medium. The complexes were extracted in chloroform medium maintaining the aqueous : non-aqueous phase at 1 : 1 and the absorbances measured at 440 nm.

Beer's law, optimum range, sensitivity and photometric error : The colour systems were found to obey Beer's law from 1 to 6 ppm and 1 to 8 ppm with reagents I and II, respectively. The Ringbom¹⁹ plots showed that the optical ranges were 1-6 ppm and 2-8 ppm with reagents I and II, respectively and the percent relative error²⁰ in this range was 2.71 and 2.72, respectively. The molar absorptivity was found to be 8.13×10^3 and 5.00×10^3 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The sensitivity according to Sandell's²¹ definition was 0.013 and 0.022 μ g of Pd^{2+} /cm².

Composition of the complexes : The composition of the complexes in solution was ascertained by Job's method²² of continuous variation with equimolar solutions (9.37×10^{-4} M) of ligands and Pd^{2+} and by mole-ratio method²³ using a constant metal ion concentration (2 ml of 1.41×10^{-3} M reagent I and 1 ml of 2.81×10^{-3} M reagent II). The composition of the complexes was found to be 1 : 2 with respect to metal : ligand.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of foreign ions on the determination of Pd^{2+} with the reagents were studied by adding several foreign ions separately at different concentrations and extracting the complexes with chloroform following recommended procedure. It was observed that 200 ppm of Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Al^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Ir^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , and 400 ppm of SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , F^- , acetate, citrate, oxalate, tartrate, EDTA have no adverse effect on the determination of 4 ppm of Pd^{2+} . Presence of Fe^{3+} upto fifteen fold has no adverse effect but Mo^{6+} , V^{5+} , W^{6+} , Os^{8+} and SCN^- seriously interfere.

Degree of dissociation and formation constants : The degree of dissociation and the dissociation constant k was calculated from the equation of Harvey and Manning²⁴. The dissociation constants were found to be 7.77×10^{-10} and 1.32×10^{-9} with reagent I and II, respectively. So the overall stability constants are 1.29×10^9 and 7.57×10^7 .

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Pd^{2+} COMPLEXES AT $27 \pm 2^\circ$

Reagent	Leden's method			Yatsimirskii's method			Harvey-Manning's method
	log k_1	log k_2	log β_2	log k_1	log k_2	log β_2	log β_2
I	4.01	3.83	7.84	4.21	3.87	8.08	9.11
II	3.70	3.08	6.78	3.88	3.40	7.28	7.96

The log k_1 and k_2 were evaluated by considering the degree of complex formation function (ϕ) and graphical extrapolation method of Leden. The stepwise formation constants were further verified by Yatsimirskii's method. The results are summarized in Table 1.

The results of application of the methods in synthetic mixture are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF APPLICATION OF THE METHODS IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Synthetic mixture	Pd ²⁺ found (mg)*	
	Reagent I	Reagent II
Pd ²⁺ = 0.1 mg, Pt ⁴⁺ = 1.0 mg, Ir ⁴⁺ = 1.0 mg, Rh ³⁺ = 1.0 mg, Ru ³⁺ = 1.0 mg, Os ³⁺ = 0.2 mg.	0.098	0.099

*Average of three determinations.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V), Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) in Presence of Each Other and in Presence of Other Ingredients Using 2,2'-Bipyridyl as Analytical Reagent

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THE microanalytical spectrophotometric determination of V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ or Ta⁵⁺ in presence of each other, in presence of other ingredients or in admixture is of interest.

Niobium(V) and tantalum(V) in presence of each other, in presence of other ingredients and in rocks containing the elements were determined using oxine, alizarin red S and quinizarin-3-sulphonic acid, as chromogenic reagents. V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, and Ta⁵⁺ were also studied spectrophotometrically using haematoxylin and murexide^{1,2}, 2,2'-bipyridyl³ and violuric acid⁴.

Experimental

Standard solutions of 10⁻³M V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, and Ta⁵⁺; and 10⁻⁴M Fe³⁺, Fe²⁺, Co³⁺, Cr⁶⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, Th⁴⁺, U⁶⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺, Ag⁺, Cu²⁺, Mg²⁺, Sr²⁺, Hg²⁺, Hg²⁺, In³⁺, Al³⁺, Sc³⁺, Y³⁺, La³⁺, Mn²⁺, Sn²⁺, Pb²⁺ and Bi³⁺ were prepared⁵ from the A. R. grades (Riedel de Hën, BDH or Merck, 99.9%) of V₂O₅, Nb₂O₅, Ta₂O₅, (NH₄)₂SO₄·FeSO₄·6H₂O, Fe₂O₃, CoCl₂·6H₂O, K₂Cr₂O₇, (NH₄)₂Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, Na₂WO₄·2H₂O, Th(NO₃)₄, UO₂(CH₃-COO)₂·2H₂O, TiO₂, ZrO(NO₃)₂, AgNO₃, CuSO₄·5H₂O, MgSO₄·7H₂O, SrCl₂·6H₂O, Hg₂(NO₃)₂·H₂O, Hg₂Cl₂, In₂(SO₄)₃·H₂O, AlCl₃, Sc(NO₃)₃·4H₂O, Y₂(SO₄)₃, La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, MnSO₄·H₂O, SnCl₂·2H₂O, Pb(CH₃COO)₂, and Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O. 10⁻³M 2,2'-Bipyridyl (bipy) was prepared⁶ by dissolving the accurately weighted amount of bipy in ethanol. Buffer solutions of pH 3.90, 10.05 and 10.36 were prepared according to standard method⁷.

Pye Unicam SP 8000 Ultraviolet Recording spectrophotometer, silica cell, 1 cm light path, and Pye Unicam Model MK 2902 pH Meter were used to record the data.

The determination of V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺ or Ta⁵⁺ in presence of each other, in admixture or in presence of other metal ions was performed by measuring the spectral absorbances at 208, 210, 215, 220, 225, 230, 235, 240, 243, 250, 260, 265, 270, 272, 275 and 278 nm using constant [bipy] at 1 × 10⁻⁵M, equal concentration of V⁵⁺, Nb⁵⁺, Ta⁵⁺ and the other metal ions (Ag⁺, Cu²⁺) at 1 × 10⁻⁷M, and larger concentrations of the other elements at 1 × 10⁻⁶M and 1 × 10⁻⁹M in buffer solutions of pH 10.36 (in the case of the determination of V⁵⁺ in presence of Nb⁵⁺, Ta⁵⁺, (Nb⁵⁺ + Ta⁵⁺) or in presence of mixture of the other elements), 3.9 (ia